

A Hospital-Based Assessment of the Prevalence of Bacterial Meningitis in Children with Apparent Febrile Seizure

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to determine the frequency of meningitis in children with FS(febrile Seizure)and related risk factors.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was performed on 550 patients aged 6 months to 6 years who had first attack of seizure with fever in the Pediatric Ward of Jawaharlal Nehru medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India from December 2021 to September 2022. Patients were divided into 2 groups. Those with simple febrile seizure with one tonic clonic seizure attack for less than 15 minutes. Those cases who had multiple attacks or seizures lasting more than 15 minutes, or had focal seizures were categorized as complex FS.

Results: Of those 300 patients were male (54.54%) and 250 were female (45.45%). In children who had not undergone an LP, meningitis could be excluded according to clinical status. The majority of patients with meningitis and all patients with bacterial meningitis were in the age group less than 18 months old. The majority of patients with meningitis had presented with their first attack of FS (45 cases, 90%) when compared with patients with a normal LP (44%) and this was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). 17 patients with meningitis (34%) and 180 patients with a normal LP (36%) were been pretreated with antibiotics before admission and this was not statistically significant. According to logistic regression analysis, independent variables for predicting meningitis were neurological deficits, postictal drowsiness, body temperature, level of Hb, and WBC. Postictal drowsiness ($p = 0.001$), neurologic deficit ($p = 0.000$), and body temperature $\geq 38.5^\circ\text{C}$ ($p = 0.032$) were among the clinical signs, which were statistically significant predicting factors for meningitis. Laboratory tests including white blood count (WBC) $\geq 15000 \text{ mm}^3$ ($p = 0.002$), and hemoglobin (Hb) $< 10.5 \text{ gr/dl}$ ($p = 0.010$) also had statistical significance in predicting meningitis.

Conclusion: In conclusion, our findings suggested that the frequency of bacterial meningitis in children who presented with febrile seizure (FS) is not high. Meningitis is more common in patients less than 18 months old with febrile seizure (FS); however, complex features of seizures, first attack of FS or impaired consciousness seem to be significant risk factors for meningitis and an LP should be in mind in this situation.

Keywords: Bacterial meningitis; Febrile seizure; children

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Introduction

Seizures occur in the context of many childhood illnesses, and account for approximately 1–5% of all emergency departments (ED) visits. [1,2] It is broadly defined as a seizure accompanied by fever without evidence of central nervous system (CNS) infections, occurring in children 6 months to 5 years of age. [3] The association between seizure and bacterial meningitis (BM) is well established. [4-6]

It is therefore imperative to rule out BM prior to making the diagnosis of FS. However, the diagnosis of FS in certain subgroups of children with an apparent FS is a challenge: FS may be the sole manifestation of BM in infants [3]; complex features of seizure can increase the risk of BM in others. [7,8] Accordingly, when these children present with an apparent FS, clinicians may remain uncertain about

the risk of BM. In acute situation, the most challenging issue is to make a decision whether a lumbar puncture (LP) is necessary to rule out BM. Knowledge of the prevalence of BM among various subgroups of children with FS can assist clinicians to make appropriate clinical decisions in such challenging situations.

Seizure can be seen in meningitis in one out of 6 patients of whom one-third have no signs of meningeal involvement. [9] Some predicting factors of meningitis in young children who present with seizure and fever may be seizure duration above 30 minutes, neurologic deficit, and postictal drowsiness. [10] Prevalence of meningitis ranges between 2.4-17% in those children who have seizure and fever. [10-12] Seizures are the first manifestation of meningitis in 16.7% of children and in one-third of these patients, whereas meningeal signs and symptoms may not be evident. [9] Therefore, it is mandatory to exclude underlying meningitis in children presenting with fever and seizure prior to making the diagnosis of febrile seizure the initial concern in these children is always to make a proper decision regarding to do an LP to exclude meningitis. Awareness of the prevalence of meningitis and its related factors in children presenting with FS to help pediatrician to make proper decisions in these situations is necessary. [13] Some of these studies suggest that in the absence of typical meningeal signs, then an LP should be considered in children with complex seizures, prior antibiotic therapy, age less than 12 months, or incomplete vaccination history. [14]

The aim of the present study was to determine the frequency of meningitis in children with FS and related risk factors.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was performed on 550 patients aged 6 months to 6 years who had first attack of seizure with fever in the Pediatric Ward of Jawaharlal Nehru medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India from December 2021 to September 2022. Patients were divided into 2 groups. Those with simple FS with one tonic clonic seizure attack for less than 15 minutes. Those cases who had multiple attacks or seizures lasting more than 15 minutes, or had focal seizures were categorized as complex FS.

The patient records were evaluated for LP for meningitis, which was defined as abnormal changes in cell count, protein, and sugar as well as positive culture result. Age, gender, seizure type and duration, postictal drowsiness, neurologic deficit, body temperature, previous family history of FS, white blood cell count (WBC), and hemoglobin (Hb) were also recorded.

The inclusion criteria included patients aged 6-18 months old with first attack of convulsion and fever. Exclusion criteria included any history of FS or epilepsy, any neurological disorder including hydrocephaly, cerebral palsy, any metabolic disorder including hypoglycemia, hypocalcemia, hypomagnesemia, traumatized LP, and incomplete records. A statistician calculated the sample size, and data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 11 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Statistical tests including chi square and t test were used. Logistic regression analysis was used to evaluate predicting factors for meningitis. Statistical significance was set at a p-value <0.05.

Results

Table 1: Clinical aspects of first seizure patients with and without meningitis

Variables	Meningitis (n=50) No. (%)	Non-meningitis(n=500) No. (%)	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-value*
Gender					
Female	20 (40%)	230 (46%)	0.820	0.334-2.154	0.854
Male	30(60%)	270 (54%)			
Age					
<18 m.	38 (76%)	240 (48%)	4.310	1.371-12.886	00.9
> 18 m.	12 (24%)	260 (52%)			
Seizure type					
Simple	8 (16%)	350 (70%)	0.064	0.019-0.234	<0.001
Complex	42 (84%)	150 (30%)			
Seizure recurrence					
First attack	45 (90%)	220 (44%)	10.435	2.354-45.262	<0.001
Recurrent attack	5 (10%)	280 (56%)			
Altered consciousness					
No	10 (20%)	470 (94%)	55.225	16.84-175.61	<0.001
Yes	40 (80%)	30 (6%)			
Pre-treatment with antibiotic					
No	33 (66%)	320 (64%)	0.890	0.337-2.436	1.00
Yes	17 (34%)	180 (36%)			

Of those 300 patients were male (54.54%) and 250 were female (45.45%). In children who had not undergone an LP, meningitis could be excluded according to clinical status. The majority of patients with meningitis and all patients with bacterial meningitis were in the age group less than 18 months old. The majority of patients with meningitis had

presented with their first attack of FS (45 cases, 90%) when compared with patients with a normal LP (44%) and this was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). 17 patients with meningitis (34%) and 180 patients with a normal LP (36%) were been pretreated with antibiotics before admission and this was not statistically significant.

Table 2: Independent variables for predicting meningitis among first seizure patients with and without meningitis

Variables	EXP(B)	95% CI lower-upper	P-value
Neurologic deficit			
Yes	28.745	2.645-322.420	0.004
No	1		
Postictal drowsiness			
Yes	3.210	1.550-6.415	0.001
No	1		
Body temperature			
$\geq 38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$	1.820	1.036-2.712	0.032
$< 38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$	1		
White blood cell count			
$\geq 15000 \text{ mm}^3$	2.462	1.340-4.070	0.002
$< 15000 \text{ mm}^3$	1		
Hemoglobin			
$< 10.5 \text{ gr/dl}$	1.891	1.150-3.240	0.010
$\geq 10.5 \text{ gr/dl}$	1		

According to logistic regression analysis, independent variables for predicting meningitis were neurological deficits, postictal drowsiness, body temperature, level of Hb, and WBC. Postictal drowsiness ($p=0.001$), neurologic deficit ($p=0.000$), and body temperature $\geq 38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($p=0.032$) were among the clinical signs, which were statistically significant predicting factors for meningitis. Laboratory tests including white blood count (WBC) $\geq 15000 \text{ mm}^3$ ($p=0.002$), and hemoglobin (Hb) $< 10.5 \text{ gr/dl}$ ($p=0.010$) also had statistical significance in predicting meningitis.

Discussion

Febrile seizures (FS) are the most common type of childhood seizures, affecting 2–5% of children older than 1 month and most commonly from 6 months–5 years old. [15,16] It is possibly a major cause of pediatric admissions worldwide. [17] febrile seizure are defined as seizures accompanied by fever without evidence of intracranial infection, metabolic disturbance, or a history of previous afebrile seizures. [18] Febrile seizures are classified as simple or complex. Simple febrile seizures lasted for less than 15 minutes and did not recur within 24 hours. Complex febrile seizures are focal, prolonged (> 15 minutes), and/or recurrent within 24 hours. [19] The majority of febrile seizure are benign, and self-limiting occur due to electrical abnormality in the brain triggered by the rapid rise of temperature. [20] However, a substantial number of them are suggestive of underlying pathology. [21,22] FS may

be triggered by fevers from viral infections, focal bacterial infections and meningitis. [23]

Of those 300 patients were male (54.54%) and 250 were female (45.45%). In children who had not undergone an LP, meningitis could be bacterial meningitis excluded according to clinical status. The majority of patients with meningitis and all patients with were in the age group less than 18 months old. The majority of patients with meningitis had presented with their first attack of FS (45 cases, 90%) when compared with patients with a normal LP (44%) and this was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). 17 patients with meningitis (34%) and 180 patients with a normal LP (36%) were been pretreated with antibiotics before admission and this was not statistically significant. Ehsanipour et al that reported 3.6% of meningitis and 1.6% of BM in children aged 6 mo.–5 yr. with FS. [24] In addition, Al-Eissa in his study in Saudi Arabia found a 3.5% frequency of meningitis and 1.5% of BM among patients aged 3mo-5 yr. with FS. [25] Ghotbi and Shiva found that prior antibiotic use is a risk factor for meningitis among children with FS. [26] Casasoprona et al concluded that in cases of prior antibiotic therapy in children with FS, an LP should be considered. [27]

According to logistic regression analysis, independent variables for predicting meningitis were neurological deficits, postictal drowsiness, body temperature, level of Hb, and WBC. Postictal drowsiness ($p=0.001$), neurologic deficit ($p=0.000$),

and body temperature $\geq 38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($p=0.032$) were among the clinical signs, which were statistically significant predicting factors for meningitis. Laboratory tests including white blood count (WBC) ≥ 15000 mm³ ($p=0.002$), and hemoglobin (Hb) < 10.5 gr/dl ($p=0.010$) also had statistical significance in predicting meningitis. Chin et al [28] performed a study in London on patients aged 29 days to 15-years-old. They found that 17% of cases of status epilepticus associated with fever had acute bacterial meningitis. They also detected that 1.2% of patients with acute bacterial meningitis had short seizure. Accordingly prolonged seizure can be an important sign of meningitis in patients with seizure and fever.

In a study by Kimia et al [29] on 704 cases aged 6 months to 18 months with first simple febrile seizure, LP was performed in 271 (38%) cases. Their study revealed that 10 cases (3.8%) had aseptic meningitis, with CSF abnormal cell count and no bacterial infection.

Meningitis is a relatively common infection in infants and young children, and is clinically diagnosed as the first complex febrile seizure (FCFS). Although no cases of bacterial meningitis (BM) were found in infants and young children with their first simple febrile seizure (FSFS), presumed viral meningitis (PVM) is not uncommon.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our findings suggested that the frequency of bacterial meningitis in children who presented with FS is not high. Meningitis is more common in patients less than 18 months old with FS; however, complex features of seizures, first attack of FS or impaired consciousness seem to be significant risk factors for meningitis and an LP should be in mind in this situation. Lack of meningeal irritation signs does not exclude meningitis especially in younger children.

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